

THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF ASEAN COUNTRIES: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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The digital economy includes all those economic processes, transactions, interactions, and activities based on digital technologies (Schilirò, 2022). The digital economy is an ecosystem where consumers, businesses, and governments exist within a digital society, engaging and creating value that benefits all stakeholders (Schilirò, 2022). Digital economy is closely linked to digital society, as the infrastructure created within the economy is the basis for the creation of a digital society (Kovac et al, 2023). The digital economy is also defined as the contribution of any economic transaction involving both digital products and digital industries to GDP (Asian Development Bank, 2021).

In contemporary discussions about the digital economy, there is a strong focus on the dynamic environment of Southeast Asia. The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) is a rapidly growing trade bloc consisting of ten member countries: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. With a total population of over 680 million, more than half of whom are under 30 years old and a combined GDP of nearly USD 3.2 trillion in 2019, ASEAN stands as the third-largest regional economy in Asia and the fifth-largest globally, trailing only the US, China, Japan, and Germany (Isono and Prilliadi, 2023; ASEAN, 2022). ASEAN is among the world's fastest-growing regions, with average real GDP growth projected to reach 4.6% in 2023 and 4.8% in 2024. By 2030, it is expected to become the fourth-largest economy globally. This growth is fuelled by a population of 700 million, consisting of young, educated, increasingly online individuals and a burgeoning middle class (Lee, 2024).

Table 1. GDP per Capita in ASEAN countries in the years 2017-2022 (U.S Dollars)

Country	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Brunei Darussalam	28,806.1	30,642.1	26,462.1	26,462.1	32,383.0	37,445.9
Cambodia	1,402.4	1,539.8	1,685.7	1,588.9	1,637.2	1,758.0
Indonesia	3,880.1	3,937.2	4,200.4	3,922.1	4,357.0	4,777.5
Lao PDR	2,472.3	2,585.0	2,627.8	2,630.1	2,586.8	2,022.0
Malaysia	9,965.2	11,079.7	11,228.3	10,400.1	11,475.6	12,448.0
Myanmar	1,152.0	1,246.6	1,223.8	1,280.1	1,317.7	1,093.2
Philippines	3,134.1	3,261.2	3,512.0	3,329.3	3,576.2	3,623.5
Singapore	61,174.4	66,823.5	66,068.1	61,298.1	77,679.7	82,794.0
Thailand	6,745.5	7,470.8	8,297.1	7,648.2	7,751.9	7,494.4
Vietnam	2,983.5	3,250.5	3,464.9	3,552.0	3,716.8	4,109.1
ASEAN	4,446.3	4,720.1	4,971.9	4,677.3	5,095.0	5,391.8

Source: ASEAN Secretariat (2023).

In 2022, the manufacturing sector was the largest contributor to ASEAN's GDP, generating US\$767 billion, which accounted for 21.2% of the total GDP. This was followed by the trade sector (14.7%), public administration and other services (10.3%), agriculture (9.8%), and real estate and business activities (6.9%). The remaining industries collectively contributed 33.8%, with net taxes on products adding another 3.3%. Notably, the accommodation and transportation industries experienced the highest growth rates in 2022, with increases of 23.8% and 16.0% respectively, reflecting a robust recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic's impact. During the peak of the pandemic, these industries were significantly affected due to lockdown measures (ASEAN Statistical Brief, 2024).

The manufacturing industry is the leading sector in many ASEAN countries, contributing 27% of GDP in Thailand, 25.4% in Myanmar, 24.8% in Vietnam, 23.4% in Malaysia, 21.6% in Singapore, and 18.3% in Indonesia. In contrast, the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector dominate in Cambodia and Lao PDR, accounting for 22.2% and 17.8% of their GDPs, respectively.

Brunei Darussalam's economy is heavily reliant on the mining and quarrying sector, which makes up 43% of its GDP, while the wholesale and retail trade sector is the primary contributor to the Philippines' economy at 18.1% (ASEAN Statistical Brief, 2024).

Since 1997, ASEAN has been engaged in digital transformation efforts, starting with the adoption of ASEAN Vision 2020, which introduced an initiative focused on advancing information and communication technology (ICT) development in the region (Suranto et al, 2023). Southeast Asia is also home to a rapidly expanding population of digital natives thriving in an exceptionally innovative environment (Murphy, 2022). Enhanced ICT infrastructure along with a tech-savvy demographic advantage, are the primary catalysts for economic growth in ASEAN (Aryani, Andari, and Suhindarto, 2022). According to the e-Conomy SEA 2022 study conducted by Google, Temasek, and Bain & Co., ASEAN had 460 million Internet users as of 2022. Remarkably, 100 millions of these users joined within the past three years. By the end of 2022, it's projected that 370 millions of these Internet users will transition into digital consumers, meaning they will purchase products and services through online channels.

This region, marked by its diverse socio-economic landscape and rapidly advancing technological infrastructure, offers a complex policy environment filled with both challenges and opportunities. The growing digital economy in Southeast Asia is underscored by multifaceted considerations encompassing technological innovation, regulatory frameworks, and socio-economic dynamics. For ASEAN countries, the digital economy is essential for driving digital transformation. The digital transformation of ASEAN countries presents immense opportunities for economic growth and development. Digitalization initiatives in Southeast Asia countries are motivated by various factors. The primary aim is to boost economic growth and enhance competitiveness globally. These efforts focus on nurturing digital industries, attracting investments, and creating job opportunities (Suranto et al, 2023).

In this context, digital transformation refers to the comprehensive integration of digital technology into all facets of business, fundamentally altering how businesses operate and deliver value to customers. The use of digital transformation between countries is also reshaping global trade through the innovation of electronic commerce (e-commerce) as a market platform for businesses across and within countries as well as in logistics, inventory, ICT, and payment systems (Ing and Markus, 2023).

The impact of digital products, often referred to as “digital technologies”, can be categorized into three levels of integration: digitization, digitalization, and digital transformation. Although these terms are often used interchangeably in the literature, recent reviews indicate that they should be seen as sequential phases (Kraus et al., 2022). Digitization refers to the shift from analog to digital information, digitalization involves how digital technologies alter business processes, and digital transformation represents the broader organizational change driven by digital technologies, resulting in new or revised business models (Kraus et al., 2022).

In details, digitization refers to the process of converting data into a digital format (Verhoef et al., 2021). Literatures also define digitization as the transformation of analog tasks into digital formats (Li et al., 2016; Sebastian et al., 2017; Horváth and Szabó, 2019) or the integration of IT into existing processes. More broadly, it is seen as the cost-effective creation (Lai et al., 2010) or facilitator of cost-effective resource configurations utilizing IT (Vendrell-Herrero et al., 2017).

Secondly, digitalization refers to the incorporation of digitized data into established production processes to achieve higher efficiency (Burkett, 2017). According to Verhoef et al. (2021), digitalization relies heavily on IT to create new business opportunities by revolutionizing established processes such as communication, distribution, and business relationship management.

The third is digital transformation, which is similar to digitalization except that it refers to a more extensive integration of digital products, such as a large enterprise involving hundreds of employees and tools in its strategic use of digital technologies (ADB, 2021). Digital transformation establishes a new business model by employing innovative business logic to generate and capture value (Verhoef et al, 2021; Pagani and Pardo, 2017). Moreover, digital transformation leverages digital technologies to facilitate cross-border interactions with suppliers, customers, and competitors (Singh & Hess, 2017; Verhoef et al., 2021).

Digital transformation is also linked to increased economic growth and productivity. For instance, a data by the Asian Development Bank (ADB) indicates that digitalization could contribute an additional USD 1 trillion to ASEAN's GDP by 2025 (ADB, 2021). The value of ASEAN's digital economy is projected to double to USD 2 trillion by 2030, driven by the Digital Economic Framework Agreement (DEFA) (ASEAN Indonesia, 2023). This projection underscores the significant economic impact digital technology can have on the region, driven by advancements in digital infrastructure, technology industries, and digital services in

education, finance, governance, and health. The ADB emphasizes the need for targeted investments and new partnerships to build capacity and skills, create an enabling environment for entrepreneurship, and promote inclusive growth across the region. Companies such as Expedia, Go-Jek, Grab, Meta, Netflix, Lazada, and Sea Group are expected to expand their teams by 10% annually as they continue their core operations. This growth rate significantly outpaces the general employment growth of 1%–3% in most Southeast Asian countries. Additionally, job opportunities for flexible workers are projected to triple by 2025 (Tobing, 2022).

Digital transformation has accelerated due to the challenges posed by COVID-19 (Srisathan & Naruetharadhol, 2022), which have spurred digital-enabled innovation globally, including in the ASEAN countries (Srisathan & Naruetharadhol, 2022; Muhamad et al., 2021). Despite a slowdown in 2022, according to Bloomberg, Southeast Asian tech start-ups raised approximately \$8.2 billion in 2020, and ASEAN had over 30 unicorns—start-ups valued at \$1 billion or more—by 2021 (Marsan, 2022). However, a significant concern in ASEAN's digital transformation is the growing digital divide both within and across countries (Ing and Markus, 2023). The digital divide, initially understood in a dichotomous way as a state of having or not

having access to ICT, is treated today as a complex and multidimensional phenomenon (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012, Vassilakopoulou & Hustad, 2021). The digital divide, once seen as a simple binary issue of having or not having access to ICT, is now regarded as a complex and multidimensional phenomenon (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012; Vassilakopoulou & Hustad, 202). Recent literature on the digital divide identifies three main types of divides: the access divide, related to access and equipment issues; the usage divide, associated with digital literacy; and the performance/capacity divide, linked to the benefits of using ICTs, particularly the Internet (Aissaoui, 2021).

Southeast Asia struggles to close the digital divide, marked by unequal access to and use of information and communication technologies (ICTs). This gap, affecting connectivity, access, usage, and skills, hinders the region's fast economic growth and technological advancement. Although Singapore and Malaysia have high internet penetration and digital literacy, countries like Laos, Cambodia, and Myanmar still face limited internet access and low digital skills. Moreover, there is a significant disparity in digital technology access between urban and rural areas in these nations (Suranto et al, 2023).

Fig. 1. Mobile Phone Density in ASEAN countries in the years 2013-2022

Notes: Cellular/Mobile Phone density (per 100 persons); ASEAN data for 2020-2021 is estimated as the data for some AMS are not available.

Source: ASEAN Secretariat (2023).

The capability of technology deployment is crucial for digital transformation, especially given the uneven deployment due to limited capabilities. ASEAN countries exhibit various digital divides, as highlighted by Ing and Markus (2023), including disparities in internet speed, usage, and technology production. According to Speedtest in 2022, Indonesia's internet speed is 21.95 Mbps. Singapore leads with 211.36 Mbps, while Cambodia (19.31 Mbps) and Myanmar (18.35 Mbps) have the lowest speeds in ASEAN.

Internet usage in ASEAN varies significantly: high-income countries have nearly 90% internet users, whereas lower middle-income countries have about 45%, and low-income countries less than 21% (Ing and Rodrik, 2022). Brunei Darussalam has the highest usage at 95%, followed by Singapore (92%) and Malaysia (89.6%). Myanmar (35.1%) and Lao PDR (33.8%) have the lowest usage rates (World Bank, 2021).

Fig. 2. Internet Services Density in ASEAN countries in the years 2013-2022

Note: Internet subscriptions per 100 persons; ASEAN data for 2020-2021 is estimated as the data for some AMS are not available.

Source: ASEAN Secretariat (2023).

In terms of technology production, high-income countries had an average of 19,000 patent applications from 2016 to 2020, compared to about 1,500 in lower-middle-income countries and fewer than 100 in low-income countries. In ASEAN, Singapore had 1,778 patent applications in 2020, followed by Indonesia with 1,309. Thailand (863), the Philippines (476), and Brunei Darussalam (5) had the fewest applications (World Bank, 2021).

The digital divide should be measured periodically to monitor progress and determine continuous improvement (Wati, Caplanova, Darmo, 2024). In Indonesian context for example, Wati, Caplanova, Darmo (2024) highlights significant disparities in digital skills across its provinces, particularly between more developed urban areas and remote, rural regions. Such factors as socio-economic status, education, geographic location, and cultural attitudes play a crucial role in shaping individuals' access to and proficiency in digital technologies.

Strengthening regional cooperation through initiatives like the ASEAN Digital Integration Framework will be crucial. ASEAN's digital integration is the use of digital and digital economy to enhance regional trade, growth, competitiveness and inclusiveness, and to achieve a stronger, more connected and resilient community. This effort encompasses enhancing interoperability, developing digital infrastructure, building human resource capacity, and establishing national legal and regulatory frameworks. The goal is to accelerate economic growth at both the regional and national levels (Isono and Prilliadi, 2023). ASEAN's digital integration involves harmonizing digital regulations, promoting digital innovation, developing digital skills and literacy, improving cybersecurity, increasing access to affordable and quality internet, and enhancing e-commerce and e-services (Hendratmoko, 2023). The adoption of emerging technologies such as AI, blockchain, and IoT can further accelerate digital transformation. Integrating digital solutions for sustainability, such as smart grids and sustainable urban planning, will also be vital for the region's future.

Despite notable strides, disparities persist in policy formulations across the region, thereby engendering a fragmented landscape marked by regulatory incongruities and varying levels of digital infrastructural development. Consequently, discerning the gaps within extant policy frameworks becomes imperative in fostering a cohesive and conducive environment for digital economic advancement. While significant progress has been made in the ASEAN, challenges such as the digital divide, cybersecurity, and regulatory issues need to be addressed. Continued investment in digital infrastructure, skills development, and regional cooperation will be essential for realizing the full potential of digital transformation in the ASEAN region.

Research dedicated to the issue of digitalization in Southeast Asia has been conducted. In a working paper entitled "State of Digitalization in the Southeast Asia Region," Suranto et al. (2023) examined a bibliometric analysis of the state of digitalization in Southeast Asia, focusing on the period from 2018 to 2023. By leveraging the Scopus database, this research conducted a comprehensive review of literature in the digital domain, identifying key trends, regional disparities, and thematic focuses within the ASEAN nations.

A similar study was conducted at the country level. Wati, Caplanova, and Darmo (2024) elaborated on the digital divide across Indonesian provinces based on the 2022 Indonesian Digital Society Index (Indeks Masyarakat Digital Indonesia/IMDI) published by the Ministry of

Communication and Informatics. It also analyzed key factors of the digital divide using data from the Indonesian Bureau of Statistics and a multiple linear regression model. The results identified three types of digital divides across Indonesian provinces related to access, usage, and outcomes of information and communication technology. Gross Regional Domestic Product per capita, wage/salary, proportion of formal labor, and size of the working-age population were identified as factors significantly affecting the digital divide. However, research dedicated to the digitalization levels of Southeast Asian countries and the identification of structural similarities is very limited.

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